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| 2

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THE BENEFITS OF INCLUDING A THERAPY DOG FOR IMPROVING SOCIAL SKILLS OF A CHILD WITH MODERATE INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT DISORDER

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Abstract

The article is about the role of a therapy dog for the development of social skills in a student with a moderate intellectual disability. Our chosen student attends a special education programme. In the research, we focused mostly on the student's social skills, such as communication, self-care (personal hygiene, eating, and dressing) and caring for others (for a therapy dog – feeding, brushing and walking the dog). We observed social skills such as releasing one's own tension, promoting positive self-esteem, expressing emotions clearly, as well as recognizing emotions, and spatial orientation (in and out of school). The research process took the form of individual treatments. We found out that the involvement of a therapy dog had an effect on improving the student's social skills. Improvements were seen in the areas of communication, self-care, recognition of emotions, release of one's own tension and spatial orientation. The most noticeable progress in the student was improvement in communication, self-care and releasing her own tension. During the sessions with the therapy dog, the student was more active and motivated and communicated loudly and confidently. She even greeted, said goodbye, thanked, asked for something, told if something bothered her, brushed her hair, put a patch and bandage on, poured water into a glass, prepared a snack, expressed the need to retreat to a corner and expressed if she was afraid of something or if she did not want to do something. She correctly determined the

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right and left side and led us appropriately to the school gym, hall and playground.

Keywords: therapy dog, social skills, moderate intellectual development disorder, special education programme

Introduction

Intellectual development disorder (hereinafter referred to as IDD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder that occurs before the age of 18. Children with IDD have significant limitations in intellectual functioning and adaptive behaviour. Intellectual abilities include learning, reasoning, problem solving, abstract thinking, and mature judgment. Adaptive skills are divided into social, conceptual, and practical areas, which include speech and communication skills, self-care, independence, social skills, learning and working abilities, functional learning skills, practical knowledge abilities, and taking care of one's safety (Vovk Ornik, 2015). Restoux (2010) agrees that children with IDD are characterized by limited intellectual abilities, such as thinking, understanding abstract concepts, memory, concentration, orientation, and communication, adding that IDD can occur at birth or after birth as a result of illness or injury. It is important that children with IDD are directed to the most appropriate education and training programme for them, as this is the only way they can optimally develop their strengths and feel comfortable in the programme (Kodrič, 2010). Students with moderate, severe, and profound IDD are placed in a special education and training programme, in which they can be educated until the age of 26 (Grubešič, 2014). There are six subjects in the special education and training programme: developing independence, general knowledge, work education, art education, music education, and physical education (Kočar Junkar and Modrej Mežnar, 2015).

Children with IDD develop speech and language comprehension slowly. They hear words but may quickly forget them, which may prevent them from understanding their meaning. If they have a picture or symbol that they can look at repeatedly, they can more easily determine the meaning (Whitaker, 2018). Various complementary therapeutic activities involving animals are increasingly being incorporated into the primary education of children with varying degrees of IDD. The most common are therapy or leisure activities involving dogs and horses. Marinšek and Tušak (2007) believe that the inclusion of dogs in the treatment of students with IDD is very effective, as dogs give them a sense of satisfaction

and importance. Because dogs are trainable, have a good sense of smell and hearing, and are very resilient, they have always been our helpers (Trampuš, 2014). Ries (2013) emphasizes that activities with the help of therapy animals contribute to improving communication. Animal-assisted therapies have a significant impact on improving a person's social, physical, emotional, and cognitive functions. Trampuš (2014) states that therapy dogs have a positive effect on children, as dogs do not like shouting and jumping, so children are calmer and more attentive to the dog's needs. Because therapy dogs are friendly to everyone and do not judge anyone, their company has a calming effect on people. Petting the dog and receiving a grateful response in return has also a calming effect. Baird et al. (2023) describe therapy dogs as obedient, calm dogs that are trained to provide companionship and support and to participate in goal-oriented structured therapies. It can happen that a therapy dog does not like certain behaviors, such as kissing and hugging, and sometimes may not want to interact with a particular individual. Dogs can also sometimes feel uncomfortable and certain events can be stressful for them. Dogs are therefore trained to be taught and adapted to the circumstances they will encounter. However, if a dog does not want something, the activity is replaced with another one that is more suitable and comfortable (VanFleet, 2024).

Tačke pomagačke is a Slovenian association for therapy with the help of dogs, offering therapies and activities with dogs, companionship, and awareness-raising among children and young people in kindergartens and schools. A therapy dog works in a therapeutic pair with its owner, who is a volunteer. Trampuš (2013) states that the dog first undergoes testing to determine whether it is suitable for work as a therapy dog. This is followed by theoretical training for the handler and then joint experience-gathering in various institutions, such as kindergartens, schools, hospitals, libraries, nursing homes, and rehabilitation centres. The training period lasts from approximately one to two years, after which the therapy pair can work independently. Therapy dogs undergo preventive veterinary examinations twice a year.

In this article, we describe the effective cooperation and inclusion of a therapy dog in the treatment of a selected girl with moderate IDD. In the form of individual treatments, we determined whether the presence of a therapy dog improves the student's social skills. In the study, we used a descriptive method, action research, and purposive sampling. Vogrinc (2008) describes action research as research consisting of phases and steps aimed at action or changes in

practice. It is important that we know exactly how we will monitor each step and how we will record its effects. This can be a diary, an essay, a questionnaire with open questions, a non-standardized interview, or even rating scales, attitude scales, or structured observation. The steps must also be evaluated at the end. Vogrinc (2008) adds that data is collected through notes taken during observation. These must be accurate and detailed, covering everything the observer hears and sees during the observation.

We conducted the research process with the aim of verifying whether the presence of a therapy dog has a beneficial effect on the student's well-being, increases her activity at work, and helps improve her social skills. In our research, we focused on the student's social skills, such as communication, self-care (personal hygiene, eating, and dressing), and caring for others (for the therapy dog—feeding, brushing, and walking the dog). We also observed social skills such as releasing tension, promoting positive self-image, clearly expressing emotions, recognizing emotions, and spatial orientation (in and outside of school). We conducted 20 observations of the student, ten of which involved the therapy dog and ten of which did not. After completing the observations, we compared the data obtained, presented it in more detail, and summarized the main findings. Due to the positive results, we would like to see therapy dogs included more often in the educational process, especially in the education of children with IDD, particularly those with more pronounced difficulties in the areas of sensorimotor skills, intellectual processing, and modest social skills.

The action plan used in the study consists of six phases.

First phase: Initial ideas

Formulating a preliminary idea and research problem based on experience

I decided to include therapy dogs in the treatment because dogs are good company and have a calming effect on people, as their presence causes the release of oxytocin, serotonin, and dopamine, and reduces cortisol and norepinephrine levels. As I was bitten by a dog when I was young, I was initially afraid of them, but over time I realized that I could trust them and that I had just been unlucky at the time. On social media, I discovered the Tačke pomagačke association and saw in photos how they have a positive impact on children's learning, as they are good company and motivate them to work. I asked the association to collaborate with me.

Second phase: Field research

Second step: Overview of events in Slovenia and literature review

Before we started planning the lessons, we reviewed the available foreign and Slovenian literature to find out what had already been done in this field and what different authors think about the inclusion of animals. A lot of good practices and visual material can be found in the book by Mojca Trampuš titled *Tačke v šoli: Terapevtski pes – učiteljev pomočnik in šolarjev sopotnik* (Paws at School: Therapy Dogs – Teachers' Assistants and Students' Companions). We decided to conduct action research, as we found only a small number of studies related to the work of therapy dogs in Slovenia.

A case study by Kogan et al. in 1999 demonstrated that therapy dogs have a positive effect on children with special needs. Two students were included in the study, one of whom, aged 11, had mild IDD, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, and depression. The other student was a hyperactive, depressed, and impulsive 12-year-old. The interaction with the dog took place every week as part of a 45- to 60-minute session, during which the students petted and brushed the dog. The 11-year-old student with mild IDD showed an increase in positive communication, which he also transferred from therapy to activities with others. His tone of voice improved and his level of patience in relationships with peers increased. The other student experienced a reduction in feelings of helplessness and an improvement in self-confidence. Both students made progress during therapy with the therapy dog (Kogan et al., 1999).

Third phase: Action planning

Third step: Preparation for sessions

Before we started planning the sessions, we identified the student's biggest problems in the area of social skills. We had to determine how the sessions would be conducted and where and when they would take place. We then agreed on the dates and content of the sessions and coordinated them with the handler.

Fourth step: Preparation of visual support for conducting sessions

We used Boardmaker visual support, which originally contains English words under the symbols. For our own use of symbols in lessons, we removed the English words so that they would not distract the student. We wrote the Slovenian word above the symbol ourselves.

Fifth step: Preparation of a checklist and visual scale of the student's well-being (in the appendices)

Fourth phase: Implementation of the action**Sixth step: Implementation of the sessions**

We conducted ten sessions without a therapy dog and ten sessions with a therapy dog. All sessions were based on learning the same skills, except that in some sessions a dog was present and in others it was not. We wanted to determine what impact the dog had on the development of these skills in our selected student. We compared the records from the sessions where the dog was present with the records from the sessions where the dog was not present.

We always demonstrated the selected skill first, then reinforced it with visual support (Boardmaker symbols) so that the student had the symbols available for a longer period of time. The student then performed the skill, while we observed her and completed a checklist.

The study included learning the following skills: how to greet people when arriving and leaving, how to ask for help, how to say thank you, how to start a conversation, how to prepare a snack, how to eat with cutlery and clean up after oneself, how to pour water into a glass and drink, how to brush one's hair, brushing teeth, washing hands, putting a bandage and plaster on your hand, finding your way around the school and outside the school (right, left, outside, inside, and finding your way to the school hall, gym, and school playground), recognizing and expressing emotions, standing up for oneself when one has had enough (NO/STOP), and releasing one's own tension (deep breathing, counting to ten, retreating to a corner, using sensory toys to calm down).

Fifth phase: Monitoring effects**Seventh step: Observing and recording events****Sixth phase: Reflection**

Even before the sessions began, I was very excited to work with the therapy dog, as I knew that the student would find it interesting and that its presence would liven up the sessions. First, there were ten sessions with the student without the therapy dog. The student was happy because the work was individual and she had a lot of time and attention. At first, she was always motivated to work, but her motivation quickly declined. She did not like having to do so many activities, as she most wanted to draw, which she loves and finds relaxing. She liked the visual aids, which she looked at with interest. She also liked our demonstration of the tasks, which she then tried to imitate.

When we finished the first ten sessions, I told the student that a therapy dog would be visiting. We wrote the dog a letter and reviewed how to behave around dogs. We also put the rules in pictures in the letter to make them easier for the student to remember. We repeated that she should sit quietly in her place, wait for permission to approach the dog and pet it, and listen carefully to instructions. She had been looking forward to its arrival since the morning and had been pointing to its picture on the poster all day. The therapy dog greatly contributed to the achievement of the set goals. During the ten sessions with the dog, she was more motivated to work, and her general well-being and level of communication improved significantly. The girl was active throughout the session and worked hard the whole time, as she was rewarded with petting the dog and giving him a treat. Because she wanted the dog to follow her and obey her commands, her communication was loud, decisive, and clear. If she spoke too quietly, she repeated the command until the dog heard her and did what she wanted. Even after the sessions were over, the progress was clearly noticeable, as she communicated better with her classmates. She was louder and used more words. It was nice to hear her speak loudly and decisively and to know that she had made progress.

Purpose and objectives

The purpose of the study was to investigate whether the presence of a therapy dog has a positive effect on improving social skills in a selected student with moderate IDD.

We focused on two research objectives:

determine whether the presence of a therapy dog influences better-developed social skills, such as communication, caring for oneself and others (e.g., caring for the therapy dog), releasing one's own tension, promoting positive self-image, clearly expressing and recognizing emotions, and spatial orientation in the student, and determine whether the student feels comfortable in the presence of the dog and is consequently more active and motivated during sessions in which the therapy dog is present.

Research questions

- Based on the selected central research objectives, we posed the following research questions:
- How does the inclusion of a therapy dog in the educational process improve the social skills of a student with moderate

IDD, such as communication, self-care, caring for others (caring for the therapy dog), releasing tension, promoting positive self-image, clearly expressing emotions, and spatial orientation (in and outside of school)?

- How does the student feel in the presence of the therapy dog (expression of feelings)?
- Is the student more active and motivated in activities when the therapy dog is involved?
- In which areas of social skills is the student's progress most noticeable after ten sessions with the therapy dog?

Methodology, sample

We used descriptive methods and action research. We used the observation technique – 20 observations were carried out, ten of which were in the presence of the therapy dog from the Tačke pomagačke association. The therapy dog Oli attended the sessions in a therapy pair with his handler. The remaining ten observations were carried out without the presence of the therapy dog.

For our study, we selected a student with moderate intellectual development disorder who is enrolled in the first level of a special education programme. The girl is six years old. She likes to socialize with her classmates, but mostly uses nonverbal communication. She uses a few words, but her voice is weak and quiet. Her communication is modest and concrete in terms of content and vocabulary, but it is understandable. She answers simple questions correctly with one word. She has not yet mastered the correct pronunciation and differentiation of sibilants and fricatives. She recognizes and names all her classmates and notices and says if someone is not in class. In the morning, she greets all her classmates and hugs them. She follows the class rules and feels comfortable in class. She chooses her own activities and toys and tidies them up after herself. She knows how to wait. She makes and maintains eye contact. She is very precise in graphomotor exercises, as she follows straight and circular lines. She is oriented in her immediate environment (school), but needs guidance and holds hands in wider environments (field trips, walks). Her artistic expression is appropriate, as she likes to colour and draw. The motif of her freehand drawings is always the same: a jellyfish. She colours alternately with both hands. She uses her right hand the most, and we encourage her to use only her right hand. She successfully sorts, strings, stacks, and groups small educational materials according to a single criterion, such as colour. She is very skilled in the area of

movement. She likes walks and playing on the school playground, where she most enjoys riding the slide. She walks on her toes; she walks in a straight line, jumps on one leg, and skips rope. She throws and catches a ball. She is in good physical condition and can walk long distances.

Data and processing methods

For the purposes of the study, we created a checklist and a visual scale to assess the student's well-being before and after the treatment. We used a checklist by author Nina D. from 2020 as a basis. We created it for the purpose of taking notes during the treatment and for easier comparison between all treatments later on. We have attached the completed table to the results section. After each treatment, we wrote down everything that happened during the treatment in detail in the form of a diary.

Since our chosen student has communication difficulties, we created a visual scale of feelings so that she could tell us how she felt before and after the treatment. She pointed to the picture that corresponded to her feelings, and we first checked whether she had chosen the right one and then circled her choice on the scale. This way, we knew exactly whether the treatment had a positive or negative effect on the student.

Image 1: Visual scale of well-being

For the action research, we developed an action plan and described in detail all the phases and steps it encompasses.

Results

We arrived at the final results by comparing the initial and final states and functioning of the student. We recorded the student's condition before the start of ten sessions with the dog, during the sessions with the dog, and after the end of ten sessions, and determined the differences in the areas of social skills that we selected for the study. In order to achieve a reliable, objective comparison of the results obtained (comparison of data in the presence and absence of the dog), we ensured that the sessions were conducted under the same circumstances, without any distractions. This ensured stable observation conditions. In the further analysis of the data, all the

research questions were addressed and both objectives were achieved, as described in more detail in the discussion.

Fine (2006) mentions how Levison, the pioneer of animal-assisted therapy, left a child with communication difficulties alone with his dog during a session. When he returned, the child was communicating with the dog. This was also the case in our example. Before the sessions with the dog, the girl was shy, quiet, and used only a few gestures. At first, she was cautious and reserved around the dog, but soon became loud, decisive, and talkative. Progress was already visible during the first session with the dog, as the girl was smiling, relaxed, more motivated, and more active at work, and did not need to retreat to a corner or relax with sensory toys. She was so excited about the dog's arrival that she pointed to a picture of the therapy dog on a poster during morning class and said that the dog would be coming soon. During systematic observation, we noticed that individual work suited the student very well, as she was more confident in this setting than in classes with several other students present.

Below are graphs that show that the girl was more active and motivated in the presence of the dog and performed the selected skills more successfully. We observed the presence of her behaviour with and without therapy dog and wrote down answers YES or NO. Based on these answers we made graphs to show the impact of a therapy dog. First there is a graph that shows results with the therapy dog and then there is a graph that shows results without the dog involved. Those two graphs include all the observed activities, used in the sessions with the student.

Third graph is a comparison bar chart that illustrates the total number of observed YES responses across five social skill domains during sessions conducted with and without the therapy dog. We made it to summarize the results more clearly. Overall, the presence of the therapy dog is associated with an increase in positive social and functional behaviors. The most notable improvements are observed in communication, releasing own tension, and spatial orientation, where total YES counts are substantially higher during sessions with the therapy dog compared to sessions without it. In particular, behaviors related to releasing own tension were rarely observed without the therapy dog but showed a clear increase when the therapy dog was present. The student began to communicate with the dog on her own initiative, was active and in a good mood throughout, and made an effort to give the dog clear and loud instructions. Self-care skills were generally well established in both

conditions; however, a moderate increase in YES responses was still evident during sessions with the therapy dog. In contrast, feelings-related behaviors remained consistently high across both conditions, indicating stability in emotional awareness regardless of the therapy dog's presence.

In summary, the results suggest that the therapy dog had a positive impact on several key domains, particularly those related to communication, self-regulation, and spatial orientation, while skills related to emotional awareness remained stable.

Graph 1: Number of YES responses by categories and subcategories in sessions without therapy dog

Graph 2: Number of YES responses by categories and subcategories in sessions with therapy dog

Graph 3: Comparison of total YES responses by categories with vs without therapy dog

Discussion

We answered the research questions posed in the study through action research.

The first research question was: "How does the inclusion of the therapy dog in sessions affect the improvement of the student's social skills, such as communication, self-care, caring for others (caring for the therapy dog), releasing tension, promoting positive self-image, clearly expressing emotions, and spatial orientation (in and outside of school)?" We can answer that the student was more motivated to communicate and more active in her work when the dog was present. We found that in the presence of the dog, she was louder and more confident and communicated more frequently. Using the checklist, we were able to determine that without the dog present, the student mostly used gestures and was passive when asked to work. The presence of the dog calmed her to such an extent that she did not need to retreat to a corner and relax with sensory toys. Progress was also evident in her orientation, as she wanted to lead the dog to the target correctly, which motivated her to make an effort in this activity. When leading the dog, she was relaxed, and her commands were appropriately loud, decisive, and understandable.

We confirmed the second research question, which was: "How does the student feel in the presence of the therapy dog?" By analysing the visual mood scale, we concluded that the student felt better in the presence of the dog than when the dog was not present during the sessions.

We also confirmed the third research question: "Is the student more active and motivated during activities when the therapy dog is present?" There was a noticeable difference in the student's activity and motivation when the dog was present during the sessions. The student was more active, more confident, and more motivated to work. The results of monitoring her mood also confirmed this.

The final research question was: "In which areas of social skills is the student's progress most noticeable after ten sessions with the therapy dog?" Based on the analysis of the data, we found that the most noticeable progress was in the area of communication about caring for oneself and others and in the area of releasing one's own tension. We came to this conclusion using diary entries and a checklist. We compared the entries and determined the extent to which she had progressed in each area when the dog was present during the sessions.

Conclusion

Our study included a student with moderate IDD who is enrolled in a special education programme. In this article, we first describe what moderate IDD is and how it affects intellectual abilities and adaptive behaviour. We emphasise the importance of communication, caring for oneself and others, releasing tension, developing a positive self-image, expressing and recognising emotions, and spatial orientation for independence and well-being. We researched literature and articles on the presence of therapy dogs in schools and recorded our findings.

Through action research, we determined the impact of a therapy dog on the social skills of a student with moderate IDD. We developed an action plan and described all the steps and phases included in the plan. The first objective was to determine whether the presence of a therapy dog influences the development of social skills such as communication, caring for oneself and others, releasing tension, recognizing emotions, and spatial orientation. The second goal was to determine whether the student feels comfortable in the presence of the dog and is therefore more active and motivated during sessions with the therapy dog than during sessions without the dog. We compared learning the same skills with and without the therapy dog. During the sessions, we completed a checklist and a visual scale of the student's well-being. We kept a daily log of events so that we could compare our findings at the end and conclude whether and to what extent the presence of the dog had a positive effect on the student.

After ten sessions with the therapy dog, the most noticeable progress was in communication, caring for herself and others, and releasing her own tension. Improvement was also noticeable in spatial orientation, namely in determining left and right directions. There was no progress in the area of emotion recognition, as the student was already able to correctly recognize her emotions before the sessions with the dog. We found that activities with the help of a therapy dog improve the social skills of the selected student with moderate IDD. The dog motivated the student to communicate, activated her to work, and consequently improved her social skills in relation to other students and the dog. In the presence of the dog, she spoke more loudly and much more than during sessions without the dog, when she mostly used only gestures, and even then, only when she really needed to. During sessions without the dog, she was passive, bored, and tense. The dog's presence relaxed her and put her in a good mood, so she felt comfortable around him. Touching and petting the

dog and its presence calmed her down, so she did not need to retreat to the corner and play with sensory toys as often. She was confident and decisive around the dog, as it obeyed her commands and did what she told it to do. However, in order for the dog to obey her, she had to give loud, clearly understandable verbal commands. If her commands to the dog were too quiet, the dog did not hear her and did not do what she wanted, which motivated her to be even louder, clearer, and more decisive in her communication.

The school's professional staff expressed interest in the possibility of incorporating the therapy dog into their educational process. They also recognized the positive effects of the therapeutic dog's presence on the student. Although the study confirmed the positive effect of the therapeutic dog's presence on the student, we are aware of its limitations. A case study was used, which means that we cannot generalize the results to the entire population. Certainly, more objective and statistically reliable data could be obtained with a larger sample of observed individuals and an increase in the number of sessions with the presence of a therapy dog. If we were to plan and conduct the sessions again, we would take more care to ensure that the student did not have too many activities in a single session. We would write the diary immediately after the session, rather than late in the afternoon, as this would allow us to capture more details about what happened during the sessions.

We confirm the positive effect of therapy dogs on well-being, and list individual elements of the educational process for children with IDD. This study thus presents an example of good planning of the special educational process with the implementation of therapy dogs, which can be followed by other professionals.

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